

THE EFFECT OF MOLECULAR WEIGHT AND PROCESSING ON ADHESION OF CARBON FIBERS TO POLYCARBONATE MATRICES

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ABSTRACT

Molecular weight of the matrix and consolidation temperature were found to have significant influence on the IFSS. The adhesion level showed increases of more than 100% across a critical molecular weight range. Above this critical level there is a monotonous increase in adhesion, but to a lesser degree. Increases of 20% to 30% in IFSS were seen for different MW ranges with increasing consolidation temperature. Increases of 8% to 15% in IFSS were seen with increasing MW for different consolidation temperatures. When selected fiber coatings of different MW were applied to the fibers, the low MW fraction has been shown to always migrate to the interface and control the level of adhesion.

INTRODUCTION

Thermoplastics are coming under increasing interest as matrices for structural composites. Just as in thermosets, adhesion between the fiber and the matrix is a critical factor to achieving the full potential of these materials in structural applications. However, whereas in thermoset matrices, the small reactants can chemically interact with the fiber surface and attain an optimum conformation as they react and solidify, thermoplastics behave in a fundamentally different manner. Adhesion of thermoplastic matrices to fibers in composites is dependent on a number of complex factors both intrinsic to the fiber and the matrix such as the morphology and mechanical properties, crystallinity or crosslinking of the matrix and extrinsic such as the processing conditions, presence of additives and impurities at the interphase [1,2]. In both cases however, knowledge about the molecular level composition and structure of the interphase is the key to understanding adhesion in these systems.

A number of matrix properties of a thermoplastic polymer is related to its molecular weight. The molecular weight is known to affect the strength, viscosity, crystallinity and the entanglement density of the matrix. In linear chain thermoplastic polymers such as polycarbonates, the mechanical properties start showing an increase only after the chain starts entangling. Below the critical molecular weight M_c , the matrix is brittle and would exhibit low strength and elongation

to break. It is well known that the chain ends act as imperfections in the chain adversely affecting the strength properties. The number of chain ends are higher in concentration in low molecular weight chains and consequently lower the strength. Above the minimum molecular weight needed to get satisfactory mechanical behavior, the strength and elongation increases towards a limiting value due to the increase in the chain entanglements. This increase in the entanglement density with increase in molecular weight also contributes to the amorphousness of the long chain polymers [3].

Though the effects of molecular weight of a thermoplastic polymer on its other properties is well documented in the literature, very little is known about its effects on the interfacial adhesion in polymer composites. A quantitative investigation of the effects of molecular weight and the processing conditions on the interfacial strength in polycarbonate carbon fiber composites was conducted to gain a better understanding of interfacial phenomena in thermoplastic composites. The interphase region between the fiber and matrix is known to be of great importance in the development of the mechanical properties of a composite material [4-6]. Though due to the complex physico-chemical interactions occurring at the interface, the interphase region might have properties very different from the bulk properties of the fiber and the matrix, the trend seems to indicate a correlation between the interphase properties and the constituent properties. Theoretical relations based on elastic stress transfer mechanisms between interfacial properties and bulk properties have been proposed by many authors. Cox [7] and later Cooke [8] have developed models in which an elastic fiber of length l , embedded in an elastic matrix under general strain ϵ .

$$\tau = E_f \epsilon_m \left(\frac{G_m}{2 E_f \ln \left(\frac{R}{r} \right)} \right)^{0.5} \left(\frac{\sinh \beta (0.5l - x)}{\cosh \beta \frac{l}{2}} \right) \quad (1)$$

where τ is interfacial shear strength, ϵ_m is the matrix strain, E_f Young's modulus of the fiber and G_m matrix shear modulus, R and r are interfiber distance and the radius of the fiber respectively. The second part of the Eqn (1) deals with the geometry of the specimen. The theory predicts a direct dependence of the interfacial shear strength on the matrix strain. Since the matrix yield strain increases with increase in molecular weight due to higher entanglement density, therefore the maximum interfacial strength at yield would be proportional to the molecular weight.

A second approach on the atomistic level dealing with the chain conformation and adsorption at the fiber matrix interface can also be used to understand the interfacial interactions. The measure of adhesion between the polymer chain and the fiber can be thought of as being dependent on the number of contact points between the active sites on the surface and the chain. Due to the constraints imposed on the number of conformations a polymer chain can have at the interface, most of the chains tend to flatten out to occupy a lower energy state [9,10]. This chain segmental orientation and conformations are seen to extend up to 3.5 times the radius of gyration R_g of the longest polymer chain. Even though, the number of polymer chains per unit area of the surface will be lower in case of the higher molecular weight polymer chains due to their longer chains lengths, the number of contact points would be more. The next layer adsorbed on top of these polymer chains would also be able to entangle more with the loops and tails and create a strong adhesive and cohesive bonding between the surface and the bulk matrix medium. The lower molecular weight polymer chains on the other hand do not lose as many number of conformations as a higher molecular weight chain [11]. Consequently the lower molecular weight chains tend to still retain a major part of their isotropic bulk conformation. This would reduce the chances of active groups on the matrix chains to interact with the surface functionalities and hence reduce the number of contact points between the polymer chain and the surface leading to lowering of the interfacial adhesion.

MATERIALS

Hercules Magnamite[®], PAN based type II, high strength AS4 6K carbon fiber tow with standard commercial oxidative treatment was used as the reinforcing fiber medium. Bisphenol-A polycarbonate which is an amorphous thermoplastic was used as the polymer medium. The polycarbonate of different molecular weight ranges were obtained from the GE Plastics Inc. Three of the four grades were received in pure form without any additives or stabilizers being added to them. The fourth grade, Lexan 8040 is FDA approved commercial grade without a UV stabilizer. Pure grades were used to preclude any effect these agents might have on the interfacial adhesion. Table 1 gives the details of the different grades of polycarbonate, their nomenclatures and the molecular weight ranges determined by gel permeation chromatography (GPC) based on light scattering absolute weight average molecular weight standards for polystyrene done on a Perkin Elmer LC30 Chromatograph.

Table:1 Molecular weights of Bisphenol-A Polycarbonate

Resin Grade	Author's nomenclature	Weight Average MW M_w	Number Average MW M_N	M_w/M_N
ML5721-111	PC100	31,135	14,382	2.165
Lexan 8040	PCFF	24,894	11,865	2.098
ML5221-111	PCHF	22,963	10,310	2.227
ML5832-111	PCOQ	16,152	7,623	2.119

EXPERIMENTAL

Thermoplastic matrix microindentation test specimens were fabricated by hot pressing fibers between pairs of matrix sheets in a Carver press. Prior to the fabrication of the final test specimens, preform sheets one half the thickness of the final specimens were first produced by hot pressing the dried polycarbonate powder between aluminum foil sheets with the thickness controlled by a surrounding dam of stainless steel. Times and temperatures for this preliminary step were kept as low as possible to minimize chances of thermal degradation, the assembly was kept sealed inside the foil throughout the process to minimize oxidation. Aluminum foil pressing sheets were employed to avoid the use of release agents which might cause surface contamination.

Pressure was maintained throughout the pressing cycle. Cooling was accomplished by a standard platen water cooling system at approximately 1 °C/second. Sample specimens having the dimensions of 2cm x 1cm were cut from the fabricated composite specimens for microindentation test and mounted and polished using standard metallographic techniques.

The microindentation tests were done on a commercially available Interfacial Testing System (ITS) developed by Dow Chemical Co. Inc. [12]. This fully automated instrument is designed to test real composite specimens. A diamond tipped indenter mounted on the objective lens of a high power optical microscope is used to indent single fibers in the composite specimen. A television camera monitor is used to observe the debonding. The force required to debond is input to a computer program which utilizes a finite element analysis algorithm derived from Mandell, *et al* [13] to calculate the interfacial shear strength.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

As can be seen from Fig. 1 and Table 2, with increased molecular weight, there is an increase in IFSS at each of the processing temperature, with a major increase between the low molecular weight grade which is below the critical molecular weight range and the next higher molecular weight grade. Above the critical limit the increase was monotonic but to a lesser degree. It was also seen that the increase in the consolidation temperature also produced increased level of adhesion except in the case of PCOQ grade, which had very poor adhesion and did not show any change in IFSS with any of the variables. For the other grades, the increase was significant between specimens fabricated at 250 °C and 275 °C, but was not much between 275 °C and 300 °C. It can therefore be inferred that the optimal processing temperature for polycarbonate carbon fiber composites lies between 275 °C and 300 °C, requiring lower times at higher temperatures for the attainment of similar level of interfacial adhesion.

Table:2 Effect of Molecular Weight and Consolidation Temperature on the IFSS

Grade	Molecular Weight M_w	Processing Temperature (°C)	Processing Time (minutes)	IFSS (MPa)
PCOQa	16,152	250	45	20.22
PCOQb	16,152	275	15	21.23
PCOQc	16,152	300	8	21.13
PCHFa	22,963	250	45	34.07
PCHFb	22,963	275	15	37.54
PCHFc	22,963	300	8	42.01
PCFFa	24,894	250	45	34.23
PCFFb	24,894	275	15	41.30
PCFFc	24,894	300	8	43.14
PC100a	31,135	250	45	36.43
PC100b	31,135	275	15	47.80
PC100c	31,135	300	8	48.32

The increase in the IFSS with the increasing molecular weight can be explained using both the elastic stress transfer mechanism and the physico-chemical interactions occurring at the interface. Interfacial adhesion is dependent upon the matrix strain. The matrix yield strain increases with increase in molecular weight due to higher entanglement density, therefore the maximum interfacial strength at yield would be proportional to the molecular weight. It was also noted during the tensile testing of pure matrix specimens that the low molecular weight specimen PCOQ, failed before yielding at around 1.3% elongation, while the elongation to yield increased from 5.5 to 5.9% for the grades PCHF and PC100 respectively.

Thermoplastic polymer matrices are generally inert and do not react chemically with the fiber surface, so the driving force for the adhesion to take place comes from enthalpic interactions like dispersive interaction between the polymer molecules and the molecules on the fiber surface. The

Figure: 1. Interfacial Shear Strength versus Molecular Weight at Different Consolidation Temperatures.

other type of interactions which are possible are polar interactions and hydrogen bond formations. The BPA polycarbonate contains polar carbonyl groups surrounded by bulky phenyl and methyl groups, so tends to behave like a non polar polymer in bulk conditions. As mentioned earlier, the polymer chains start losing conformations as they near the interface, tending to flatten out to occupy a lower energy state. This is more so in case of the higher molecular weight chains compared to the lower molecular weight chains, which tend to retain a major part of their isotropic bulk conformations. The uncoiling and flattening of the longer chains of higher molecular weight at the interface would allow more polar components to interact with the fiber surface functionalities present on the fiber surface and increase the work of adhesion, thereby increasing the interfacial shear strength for higher molecular weight specimens.

The increase in IFSS with increasing consolidation temperature can be due to the lowering of the matrix viscosity at elevated temperature and the consequent improvement in the fiber wetting by the matrix. The large increase in the IFSS between 250°C and 275°C might be due to the fact that the polycarbonate has a large drop in viscosity around 275°C and behaves like a Newtonian fluid and specimens consolidated at higher temperatures would be able to completely uncoil and diffuse through the fiber bundles and adsorb more strongly on to the fiber surface. Work done by Brady et al. [14] and Stone et al. [15] leads to a similar conclusions. Brady et al. did annealing experiments on the unidirectional polycarbonate/carbon fiber composites and found that the interfacial toughness increased with annealing time and temperature. Stone et al. observed similar results for the compressive strength development. They attributed the increase in strength and toughness above the melting point to adsorption of the matrix onto the fiber.

Segregation by Molecular Weight

In order to determine which molecular weight fraction has the strongest influence on adhesion in polydisperse systems, another series of experiments was performed in which one selected molecular weight was coated onto the fibers to a thickness of about 100nm. These coated fibers were then fabricated into specimens with a different molecular weight. Two cases were studied. In one, the low molecular weight PCOQ was coated on the AS4 fibers and then fabricated into samples (PCOQ100) where the bulk matrix was the high molecular weight PC100 and in the other the high molecular weight PC100 was coated onto AS4 fibers and then fabricated into specimens (PC100OQ) where the low molecular weight PCOQ was the matrix. Sample sets were consolidated in the same manner as before. All the samples were consolidated at 275 °C in increments of 15 minutes and the adhesion was measured by the ITS method. In both cases the adhesion changed with time as shown in Fig. 2 and Table 3. (For Reference the IFSS for the PCOQ and PC100 are included on the graph). However, the equilibrium level of adhesion was that of the bulk low molecular weight material. This indicates that if the low molecular weight material is placed at the fiber surface initially, it remains there. If it is present in the bulk it will diffuse to the interface and displace the high molecular weight material. In polydisperse systems or in commercial formulations using low molecular weight additives, if equilibrium is reached during processing, adhesion will be low because of the strong preference of the low molecular weight material for the fiber surface.

Table:3 Segregation of Matrix by Molecular Weight at the Interface

Sample Designation	Coating MW	Bulk MW	Consolidation Temperature (°C)	Time (minutes)	IFSS (MPa)
PCOQb	16,152	16,152	275	15	21.23
PCOQ100a	16,152	31,135	275	5	17.60
PCOQ100b	16,152	31,135	275	15	21.54
PCOQ100c	16,152	31,135	275	30	23.30
PCOQ100d	16,152	31,135	275	45	23.70
PC100OQa	31,135	16,152	275	5	32.68
PC100OQb	31,135	16,152	275	15	28.98
PC100OQc	31,135	16,152	275	30	23.40
PC100b	31,135	31,135	275	15	47.80

CONCLUSIONS

The effect of molecular weight on adhesion of amorphous thermoplastics to carbon fibers was investigated. It was found that the interphase controlled the adhesion because of the composition of that region. The polycarbonate/carbon fiber composite fabricated from four different molecular weight grades and at different processing temperatures proved that the interfacial shear strength increases with an increase in both molecular weight and processing temperature. The increase is seen to be significant between the low molecular weight PCOQ grade and the next higher

molecular weight grade. This increase in the IFSS ranged from 70-100%. Above this critical molecular weight range, the increase was seen to be monotonic but to a lesser extent, ranging from 8-15% for different consolidation temperatures and 20-30% for different molecular weight ranges with increasing consolidation temperatures. When the interphase was deliberately changed by the introduction of a different molecular weight material, it was found that the low molecular weight material always segregated to the interphase and controlled the resulting adhesion as measured by the interfacial shear strength method.

Figure 2: Interfacial Shear Strength versus Consolidation Time at 275°C for Fibers Coated with Different Molecular Weights.

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